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Predictive Analytics Using Machine Learning in XLSTAT

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Introduction

Predictive analytics is one of division of advanced analytics usually utilized for predicting unacquainted forthcoming events. Techniques like data mining, modeling, artificial intelligence, statistics, and machine learning are utilized in predictive analytics for analyzing current data and predicting unacquainted forthcoming events. The paper is an attempt to understand how predictive analytics can be performed using Machine Learning in XLSTAT. Paper also covers two types of models used in predictive analytics. The paper briefly explains the application of different predictive models as well as the application of predictive analytics in various industries.

1.1 Predictive analytics and machine learning

Predictive analytics uses various statistical techniques (including machine learning, predictive modeling and data mining) and uses statistics (both historical and current) to estimate, or 'predict', future results. Predictive analytics assists us with understanding possible future occurrences by dissecting the past ("Sas.com", 2021).

Machine learning, on the other hand, is a subfield of computer science that, gives 'computers the capacity to learn without being explicitly programmed'. Machine learning developed from the investigation of pattern recognition and investigates the notion that algorithms can learn from and make predictions on data. And, as they become more 'intelligent', these algorithms can conquer program instructions to make profoundly accurate, data driven decisions (Nithya and Ilango, 2017).

Predictive analytics is driven by predictive modeling. It is largely an approach than a process. Predictive analytics and machine learning go hand-in-hand, as predictive models typically include a machine learning algorithm. These models can be trained over the long run to respond to new data or values, delivering the outcomes the business needs. Predictive modeling largely overlaps with the field of machine learning.

There are two sorts of predictive models. They are Classification models, that predict class membership, and Regression models that predict a number. These models are then made up of algorithms (Charleonnann and Fufaung, 2016). The algorithms play out the data mining and statistical analysis, determining trends and patterns in data. Predictive analytics software solutions will have implicit algorithms that can be utilized to make predictive models. The algorithms are defined as 'classifiers', identifying which set of categories data belongs to.

Predictive Models

1. Decision trees:

Decision trees are a straightforward, yet powerful type of multiple variable analysis. They are created by algorithms that recognize various ways of splitting data into branch like segments. Decision trees partition data into subsets based on categories of input variables, helping you to understand someone's path of decisions.

2. Regression (linear and logistic):

Regression is one of the most popular methods in statistics. Regression analysis estimates relationships among variables, finding key patterns in large and different data sets and how they relate to each other.

3. Neural networks:

Patterned after the operation of neurons in the human brain, neural networks (also called artificial neural networks) are a variety of deep learning technologies. They're typically used to take care of complex pattern recognition problems – and are incredibly valuable for analyzing large data sets. They are great at handling nonlinear relationships in data – and function admirably when certain variables are obscure.

4. A few other methods:

1. **Time Series Algorithms:** Time series algorithms sequentially plot data and are helpful for forecasting continuous values over time.
2. **Clustering Algorithms:** Clustering algorithms organize data into bunches whose individuals are similar.
3. **Outlier Detection Algorithms:** Outlier detection algorithms center around anomaly detection, identifying items, events or observations that don't conform to an expected pattern or standard within a data set.
4. **Ensemble Models:** Ensemble models utilize multiple machine learning algorithms to obtain preferred predictive performance over what could be obtained from one algorithm alone.
5. **Factor Analysis:** Factor analysis is a technique used to depict variability and aims to find independent latent variables.
6. **Naïve Bayes:** The Naïve Bayes classifier allows us to predict a class or category based on a given set of features, using probability.
7. **Support vector machines:** Support vector machines are regulated machine learning techniques that utilization associated learning algorithms to analyze data and perceive patterns.

Applications

Predictive analytics is most commonly utilized for security, marketing, operations, risk and fraud detection. Here are only a couple examples of how predictive analytics and machine learning are used in various industries (Shin et al. (2014)):

Banking and Financial Services: In the banking and financial services industry, predictive analytics and machine learning are utilized in conjunction to detect and reduce fraud, measure market risk, identify opportunities and a whole lot more.

Security: With cyber security at the highest point of each business' agenda, it should not shock anyone that predictive analytics and machine learning play a critical part in security. Security institutions typically utilize predictive analytics to improve services and performance, yet additionally to detect anomalies, fraud, understand consumer behavior and enhance data security.

Retail: Retailers are using predictive analytics and machine learning to understand consumer behavior; who purchases what and where? These questions can be readily answered with the predictive models and data sets, helping retailers to plan ahead and stock items based on seasonality and consumer trends – improving ROI significantly.

XLSTAT Machine Learning methods

This study highlights the various machine learning techniques that are available in XLSTAT ("Help.xlstat.com", 2021).

Following methods are explained:

1. K-means clustering
2. Fuzzy K-means clustering
3. Gaussian Mixture models
4. Classification and regression trees
5. K nearest neighbors
6. Naïve bayes classifier
7. Support Vector Machine
8. Classification and regression random forests
9. Association rules

For each of this method, a brief description is provided which is followed by the input template as per XLSTAT and output is also mentioned.

1. K-means clustering

Description: K-means clustering is one of the simplest machine learning algorithm which distributes n observations into k clusters such that each of the observation belongs to the cluster with nearest mean also known as cluster centers or cluster centroid.

Input Template:

The screenshot shows a dialog box titled "k-means clustering" with a close button (X) in the top right corner. The dialog has five tabs: "General", "Options", "Missing data", "Outputs", and "Charts". The "General" tab is selected. The "Observations/variables table:" section has a text input field. Below it are three checkboxes: "Column weights:", "Row weights:", and "Row labels:". To the right of these are three radio buttons: "Range:", "Sheet", and "Workbook". The "Sheet" radio button is selected. Below the radio buttons are two checkboxes: "Column labels" (checked) and "Row labels:". At the bottom left is a "Clustering criterion:" dropdown menu set to "Determinant(W)". At the bottom right is a "Number of classes:" section with "from:" and "to:" labels, both set to "5". At the bottom of the dialog are three buttons: "OK", "Cancel", and "Help". There are also three small utility icons (refresh, edit, save) on the left side of the bottom bar.

Output: The n observations are split into k clusters with nearest means.

2. Fuzzy K-means clustering

Description: Fuzzy clustering is a type of clustering where data points can be classified to more than one clusters. Data points in the same cluster are as similar as possible and data points belonging to different clusters are dissimilar as possible.

Input Template:

Output: Unlike K-Means, Fuzzy K-means clustering results in softer clusters with some overlapping of data points.

3. Gaussian Mixture models

Description: Gaussian Mixture Models or GMMs are based on the assumption that there is certain number of distributions, and each of the distributions represents a cluster. Hence, a GMM tends to group the observations belonging to a single distribution together.

Input Template:

Gaussian Mixture Models

General | Options (1) | Options (2) | Missing data | Outputs | Charts

Observations/variables table: Range:

Observation weights: Sheet

Partial labelling: Workbook

Variable labels

One-dimensional Observation labels:

Multidimensional

OK Cancel Help

Output: Unlike K-Means, GMM clustering results in softer classification.

4. Classification and regression trees

Description: A classification tree means an algorithm in which the target variable is fixed or categorical. This algorithm is used to identify the “bracket” where the target variable would most likely fall. A regression tree is an algorithm which is used to predict the value of the target variable.

Input Template:

Output: Classification trees are used to classify data and Regression trees are used to predict data.

5. K nearest neighbors

Description: K nearest neighbors (k-NN) algorithm is a machine learning method used for classification and regression. When a new data point is considered, the technique calculates the distance from the new data point to all other points in the data-set. Based on this value, nearest neighbors are identified.

Input Template:

K Nearest Neighbors

General | Options | Prediction | Missing data | Outputs

Learning set: Range:

Y / Qualitative variable: Sheet

Workbook

Data type: Qualitative Variable labels

X: / Explanatory variables

Quantitative: Weights

Qualitative:

OK Cancel Help

Output: In k-NN classification, the output is class membership and in k-NN regression the output is predicted value.

6. Naïve bayes classifier

Description: Naïve Bayes classifier is a simple machine learning classification algorithm. It works on Bayes theorem of probability to predict the class of unknown data sets. It assumes the independence among predictors.

Input Template:

Naive Bayes classifier

General | Options | Validation | Prediction | Missing data | Outputs

Training set: Range:

Y / Qualitative variable: Sheet

Workbook

X / Explanatory variables: Variable labels

Quantitative:

Qualitative:

OK Cancel Help

Output: Naive Bayes model is relatively easy to build and very useful for large data sets. The output is the classification of the data.

7. Support Vector Machine

Description: Support vector machines (SVMs) are flexible supervised ML algorithms which are used for both classification and regression. But generally, they are used for classification related problems.

Input Template:

The screenshot shows the 'Support Vector Machine (SVM)' dialog box. It has a title bar with a close button (X). Below the title bar are tabs for 'General', 'Options', 'Validation', 'Prediction', 'Missing data', and 'Outputs'. The 'General' tab is selected. The dialog contains the following elements:

- Response variable:** An empty text input field.
- Response type:** A dropdown menu set to 'Qualitative'.
- X / Explanatory variables:**
 - Quantitative: An empty text input field.
 - Qualitative: An empty text input field.
- Classification options:**
 - Binary
 - One versus one
 - One versus all
- Output options:**
 - Range: An empty text input field.
 - Sheet
 - Workbook
- Labeling options:**
 - Variable labels
 - Observation labels: An empty text input field.
 - Observation weights: An empty text input field.

At the bottom of the dialog are four small icons (refresh, edit, save, undo) and three buttons: 'OK', 'Cancel', and 'Help'.

Output: The SVM algorithm builds a model that classifies new examples to one category or the other.

8. Classification and regression random forests

Description: This machine learning algorithm allows to make predictions based on multiple decision trees. Random forests help to provide predictive models for classification and regression. In classification, the model allows predicting the observation to a class and in regression, the model builds a predictive model.

Input template:

Classification and regression random forests

General | Options | Validation | Prediction | Missing data | Outputs | Charts

Response variable(s):

Response type: Qualitative

X / Explanatory variables:

Quantitative:

Qualitative:

Range:

Sheet

Workbook

Variable labels

Observation labels:

OK Cancel Help

Output: The multiple decision trees are used either for classification or regression.

9. Association rules

Description: Association rule machine learning is a rule-based technique for discovering interesting relationships between variables in large databases. It identifies strong rules discovered in databases using some measures.

Input Template:

The screenshot shows the 'Association rules' dialog box with the following settings:

- Items:** [Empty text box]
- Data format:** Transactional
- Range:** [Empty text box]
- Sheet:** Selected (radio button)
- Workbook:** Not selected (radio button)
- Labels included:** Checked (checkbox)
- Transactions:** Not checked (checkbox)
- Target items:** [Empty text box]
- Minimum support:** 0.05
- Minimum confidence:** 0.05
- Min. number antecedent:** 1

Output: The algorithm identifies associations between items in the form of rules. Since the data is vast, the search for rules is limited to the most important ones.

Conclusion

Predictive analytics is one of division of advanced analytics usually utilized for predicting unacquainted forthcoming events. Techniques like data mining, modeling, artificial intelligence, statistics, and machine learning are utilized in predictive analytics for analyzing

current data and predicting unacquainted forthcoming events. Predictive analytics has several applications in various industries. Machine learning algorithms are commonly used for predictive modeling and are based on several methods. XLSTAT covers a broad range of various machine learning techniques. It is relatively simple and convenient to use and has broad applications in various industries.

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